

Perioperative mortality rate and its predictors after emergency laparotomy at Debre Markos comprehensive specialized hospital, Northwest Ethiopia: 2023: retrospective follow-up study

Megbar Dessalegn^{1*}, Ayenew Negesse¹, Tilahun Deresse¹, Molla Yigzaw Birhanu¹, Eskeziyaw¹, Agedew Gedefaw Dires¹

¹ Department of Surgery, School of Medicine, Debre Markos University, Debre Markos, Ethiopia

*Correspondence: megbardessalegn@yahoo.com

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ABSTRACT

Background: Emergency laparotomy is abdominal surgery associated with a high rate of mortality. Emergency surgeries are expected to have three times mortality risk than planned surgeries. However, postoperative mortality risk is not evenly distributed across the postoperative period. The disparity in perioperative mortality occurs in the presence of comparable postoperative complication rates reported from LMICs and high-income countries. A global target was set aiming that 80% of countries by 2020 and 100% of countries by 2030 will track perioperative mortality. There are few reports on rates and predictors of postoperative mortality, whereas disease related or time specific studies are limited. Understanding the rate and predictors of mortality in the first 30 days (perioperative period) is important for evidence based decision and counseling of patients. The objective of the study was to estimate perioperative mortality and its predictors after emergency laparotomy at Debre Markos Comprehensive Specialized Hospital in Northwest Ethiopia: 2023.

Methods: This was a Hospital-based retrospective follow-up study conducted at Debre Markos Comprehensive Specialized Hospital in Ethiopia among patients who had undergone emergency laparotomy between January 1, 2019 and December 31, 2022. Sample of 418 emergency laparotomy patients selected with simple random sampling technique were studied. The data were extracted from March 15, 2023 to April 1, 2023 using a data extraction tool, cleaned, and entered into Epi-Data software version 3.1 before being exported to STATA software version 14.1 for analysis. Predictor variables with P value < 0.05 in multivariable Cox regression were reported.

Results: Data of 386 study participants (92.3% complete charts) were analyzed. The median survival time was 18 days [IQR: (14, 29)]. The overall perioperative mortality rate in the cohort during the 2978 person-days of observations was 25.5 per 1000 person-days of follow-up [95%CI: (20.4, 30.9)]. Preoperative need for vasopressor [AHR: 1.8 (95% CI: (1.11, 2.98))], admission to intensive care unit [AHR: 2.0 (95% CI: (1.23, 3.49))], longer than three days of symptoms [AHR: 2.2 (95% CI: (1.15, 4.02))] and preoperative sepsis [AHR: 1.8 (95% CI: (1.05, 3.17))] were identified statistically significant predictors of perioperative mortality after emergency laparotomy.

Conclusions: The perioperative mortality rate is high. Preoperative need for vasopressors, admission to intensive care unit, longer than three days of symptoms and preoperative sepsis were predictors of increased perioperative mortality rate.

Key words: Emergency laparotomy, Survival, Post-operative outcome, Mortality

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